

ANALYSIS OF MODERN METHODS OF FOOD DRYING

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Abstract. Drying is a complex technological process widely used in various sectors of the food industry. The functional properties of food components, which change significantly during drying, have a significant impact on their application and commercial value. This review analyzes the relationships between various food drying methods based on research from the last two decades. Finally, the impact of modern dehydration methods, including microwave, ultrasound, and infrared dehydration, as well as vacuum impregnation and dry thermal phosphorylation, on the efficiency and quality of the drying process is summarized.

Introduction

A food system is characterized by a set of physicochemical properties that determine its functional characteristics. These functional properties can be altered by technological processes at various stages of food preparation, processing, storage, and consumption. The wide range of these properties is primarily due to the presence of proteins, carbohydrates, and lipids, whose structural features determine their behavior in food systems. These components, both individually and in interactions, shape the desired sensory characteristics of the final product. Along with maintaining nutritional value during processing, it is also important to evaluate sensory properties, which can be accomplished either directly through tasting or indirectly through establishing a relationship with functional characteristics [1].

Functional properties are defined as characteristics that determine the behavior of food products during production, processing, storage, and consumption. These include water-holding capacity (the ability to retain its own and added moisture), oil-holding capacity, emulsifying properties (associated with the reduction of interfacial tension between hydrophilic and hydrophobic components), foaming capacity, gelling (the formation of a three-dimensional structure due to the interaction of proteins and carbohydrates), whipping capacity (air retention in the system), and viscosity (resistance to deformation under the influence of external forces) [2].

The quality of food products, including nutritional, sensory, physicochemical, and organoleptic properties, as well as technological characteristics (e.g., dough workability or meat product slicability), is largely determined by their functional properties. Therefore, these properties play a key role both in the processing of raw materials and in the development of food product formulas [3].

Current trends in drying for improving the functional properties of food products. Traditional drying methods are accompanied by a number of adverse changes in plant materials, including significant shrinkage, color change, oxidation of functional components, and deterioration of the nutritional and organoleptic value of the product. This ultimately leads to a decrease in its consumer characteristics. Therefore, the use of low-temperature drying modes and a reduction in drying time through the use of modern technologies aimed at intensifying heat and mass transfer processes are relevant. Analytical solutions to the thermal diffusion equation exist for cases where the material surface is exposed to a thermal pulse such as the Dirac delta function. In particular, a solution for a semi-infinite adiabatic body is presented in [4].

I. Microwave drying. Microwave drying offers several advantages over traditional convection methods, including more uniform and energy-efficient heating and accelerated moisture removal due to the volumetric energy supply directly to the product. The elimination of the need for heat transfer from the surface to the interior of the material intensifies the drying process and reduces its duration. Furthermore, microwave units require less production space (20–35% of traditional systems) and can reduce overall drying time by up to 90% [4, 5].

Additional benefits include reduced water and chemical consumption, increased equipment productivity, selective heating of the product (without significant heating of the equipment), and the ability to instantly start and stop the process, which contributes to increased cost efficiency [6].

To evaluate the effect of microwave power on the properties of food products, Behar et al. [7] investigated the drying process of Maltese cabbage peel and leaves at a power of 100–850 W. It was found that the maximum water-holding capacity of the peel (10.252 g/g) was achieved at 180 W, and the oil-holding capacity (3.795 g/g) at 700 W. For the leaves, the best values of these indicators were observed at 850 and 180 W, respectively. Moreover, drying at 450 W ensured the maximum content of extractable phenolic compounds.

In other studies [8], microwave drying (40–70°C) in combination with ethanol pretreatment was used to extract dietary fiber from peach pomace.

Higher temperatures and lower ethanol-to-sample ratios were shown to yield better functional properties, which is attributed to enzyme inactivation during processing.

II. Ultrasonic drying. High-intensity ultrasound is characterized by the use of powers of $10\text{--}1000\text{ W cm}^{-2}$ at frequencies of $20\text{--}1000\text{ kHz}$, in contrast to low-intensity ultrasound ($5\text{--}10\text{ MHz}$, $<1\text{ W cm}^{-2}$). Its impact leads to structural changes in the material and the initiation of chemical processes, which allows for the effective use of ultrasound in homogenization, extraction, drying, and enzyme inactivation technologies [9].

When an ultrasonic wave passes through a solid, alternating compression and expansion processes occur (the so-called "sponge effect"), facilitating the movement of moisture through capillaries and its removal. An additional intensification mechanism is acoustic cavitation, which ensures the destruction of bound moisture. Furthermore, mechanical vibrations reduce the surface tension forces that retain moisture in the material [10].

Studies of the effect of ultrasound power ($0\text{--}100\text{ W}$) on drying kinetics have shown that increasing the power to 100 W intensifies the process and maintains a high rate of moisture removal without a pronounced saturation period. Furthermore, the use of ultrasound preserves the quality of food products by reducing processing time and lowering the drying temperature.

Thus, Sarabia et al. [11] studied the effect of high-intensity ultrasound (20 kHz , 100 W) in combination with convective drying ($20\text{--}55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, air velocity $1.7\text{--}2\text{ m/s}$) on various vegetables. It was found that the use of ultrasound not only accelerates the process but also increases its efficiency, achieving a final moisture content of less than 1% . Moreover, after 30 minutes of processing at 55°C , the sample weight reduction was up to 94% with the use of ultrasound, while without it it was about 60% .

III. Infrared drying. Infrared heat treatment is based on the action of electromagnetic radiation with a wavelength of $1.8\text{--}3.4\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and is used to dehydrate various materials, including food products. Infrared radiation excites water molecules, causing them to vibrate, resulting in rapid internal heating and an increase in water vapor pressure within the material [12].

Compared with traditional drying methods, infrared processing offers several advantages, including higher process speed, reduced energy consumption, uniform temperature distribution, and improved final product quality. The kinetics of infrared drying depends on a number of factors, such as material density, radiation wavelength, distance from the energy source, and

airflow velocity. In general, increasing temperature, decreasing relative humidity, and reducing particle size contribute to intensifying the drying process [13].

Studies of the effect of infrared radiation on the properties of food products have shown that processing barley at a surface temperature of 105–150°C leads to a decrease in density due to an increase in volume, a decrease in the solubility of proteins due to their denaturation, an increase in the degree of starch gelatinization (up to 90%), and an increase in water absorption capacity up to 200–300% [14].

In [7], it was found that increasing the infrared drying temperature (40–70 °C) leads to a decrease in the water-holding capacity of the peel (from 9.48 to 5.47 g water/g) and the oil-holding capacity of the leaves (from 3.93 to 2.36 g/g). This is due to more pronounced destruction of the cellular structure and changes in the osmotic properties of the material, which also affects the rehydration processes. At the same time, higher temperatures contribute to better preservation of the total content of phenolic compounds.

IV. Vacuum drying. Although infrared drying does not always provide the desired improvement in the functional properties of the product, combined methods including vacuum impregnation demonstrate higher efficiency. Thus, Castagnini et al. and Moreno et al. showed that the use of vacuum impregnation in combination with various drying methods helps to improve the physicochemical characteristics of the final product. They investigated the process of enrichment of apple slices with folic acid using vacuum impregnation and ohmic heating at 30–50°C, followed by hot air drying at 50–70°C. Vacuum impregnation was carried out at a pressure of 5 kPa for 5 min, while ohmic heating was carried out at a frequency of 60 Hz and a voltage of 100 V, creating an electric field of 13 V/cm. The use of ohmic heating ensured rapid and uniform heating of the product by converting electrical energy into thermal energy, while vacuum impregnation facilitated mass transfer through pressure gradients and capillary effects. According to the results obtained, the optimal regime was a combination of vacuum impregnation and ohmic heating at 50°C followed by drying at 60°C, which resulted in a product with a higher folic acid content [14, 15].

Castagnini et al. [15] investigated the introduction of cranberry juice into apple discs using vacuum impregnation followed by stabilization by convective drying (30–50°C) or lyophilization. It was found that convective drying leads to a decrease in the anthocyanin content, whereas lyophilization allows for their preservation with virtually no loss. The best quality indicators were achieved with

lyophilization, as well as with air drying at 40°C, ensuring the preservation of the high antioxidant activity of the product.

V. Freeze drying. Freeze-drying is one of the most effective methods of food dehydration, based on the removal of moisture by converting ice directly into vapor under reduced pressure. This method maximizes the preservation of the material's structure, as the process occurs without a liquid phase, preventing the destruction of cellular tissue. The main advantages of freeze-drying are the high quality of the final product, the preservation of biologically active substances, vitamins, and aromatic compounds, as well as minimal changes in color and texture. Furthermore, products obtained by this method have high rehydration capacity. The kinetics of the process depend on the freezing temperature, the system pressure, the product layer thickness, and the heat supply condition. Despite high energy consumption and the length of the process, freeze-drying is widely used to produce high-added-value products. Research shows that freeze-drying provides better preservation of antioxidant activity and functional properties compared to convective and infrared drying, making this method promising for the production of high-quality food products [16].

Conclusions

An analysis of modern drying methods has shown that traditional dehydration technologies often lead to a deterioration in the functional and organoleptic properties of food products. At the same time, the use of innovative approaches, such as microwave, ultrasonic, and infrared drying, helps intensify heat and mass transfer processes, reduce processing time, and improve energy efficiency. Of particular interest are combined methods involving vacuum impregnation and ohmic heating, which ensure more uniform moisture distribution and the preservation of biologically active components. These technologies have been shown to significantly improve the quality of the final product, including its textural, sensory, and functional characteristics. Thus, the implementation of modern and combined drying methods is a promising direction in the development of food processing technologies

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